

Geochemistry, Geophysics, Geosystems

Dataset for

Subduction-induced back-arc extension versus far-field stretching: Contrasting modes for continental marginal break-up

Shuting Yang¹, Zhong-Hai Li^{1*}, Bo Wan², Ling Chen^{2,3}, Boris J.P. Kaus⁴

¹Key Laboratory of Computational Geodynamics, College of Earth and Planetary Sciences, University of Chinese Academy of Sciences, Beijing, China

²State Key Laboratory of Lithospheric Evolution, Institute of Geology and Geophysics, Chinese Academy of Sciences, Beijing, China

³CAS Center for Excellence in Tibetan Plateau Earth Sciences, Beijing, China

⁴Institute of Geosciences, Johannes Gutenberg University of Mainz, Mainz, Germany

Contents of files

List of data files

Model-1- η opsz2.8e19- η spsz2.8e22.zip
Model-2- η opsz2.8e22- η spsz2.8e19.zip
Model-3- η opsz2.8e20- η spsz2.8e20.zip
Model-4- η opsz2.8e23- η spsz2.8e23.zip
Model-5- γ -50.zip
Model-6- γ -100.zip
Model-7- γ -300.zip
Model-8- γ -500.zip
Model-9-500km60°.zip
Model-10- η Im-1.zip
Model-11- η Im-10.zip
Model-12- η Im-30.zip
Model-13- η Im-100.zip
Model-14- η Im-300.zip
Model-15-MOR.zip
Model-16-D+L4050km5.6e18.zip

Visualization processes: Unzip data files from a model and visualize by ParaView.